

Women's Role in Society and Family

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Abstract

There is a massive change in women's roles and family structure in most countries in recent decades. These relational and structural changes have interacted with attitudes and values relating to gender roles and the family. Topics include views on the adoption of non-traditional roles by women in the paid labour market, politics, and in society; the purpose and nature of marriage; intergenerational relations within families in general and the care of the elderly in particular; and having and raising children. Apart from it, the Woman's plays a KEY ROLE: in the socio-economic development of the Society.... The purpose of introducing a literacy programme is to raise the Society as education will enable Women to respond to the opportunities, to challenge their traditional roles and to change circumstances of life.

Introduction

Women are the indispensable part of society. Their Education influence the coming generation. The development of future generation depends upon the education of women section. So the Education of women is realised to be the essential part for the development of Society. It can help every woman to educate their children to be a good manager of the family as well as the active member of the Society. The children learn their manners and behaviour at home, and most mothers are responsible for cultivating good practice in their children. Every educated woman can run her house well, and make it a paradise on earth. Every educated woman can think well about her future and her aim in life and then choose the appropriate subject which will be useful to her throughout life. In a democratic system, the position of women is equal with that of men. Nowadays women are also conscious of their rights and obligations.

Role in the Family and Society of Women

Women are the pioneers of the nation. Indian culture gives importance to women, comprising half of the population of the world. Women constitute 50% of human resources, the most significant human resource next only to the man having great potentiality. Women are the key to sustainable development and quality of life in the family. Various roles of the women assume in the family are those of wife, leader, administrator, manager of family income and last but not the least important the mother.

As A Wife

A Woman is man's helpmate, partner and comrade. She sacrifices her pleasure and ambitions, sets the standard of morality, relieves stress and strain, the tension of the husband, maintains peace and order in the household. Thereby she creates the environment for her partner to think more about the economic development of the family. She is the source of inspiration for the high endeavour and worth achievements in life. She stands by him in all the difficult situations as well as she shares all success and results. She is the person to whom he turns for love, sympathy, understanding, comfort and recognition. She is the symbol of purity, faithfulness and submission and devotion to her husband.

As an Administrator and Leader of the Household

A well-ordered household is essential to normal family life. The woman in the family assumes this function. She assigns duties among family members according to their interest and abilities. In the preparation and serving of meals, selection and care of clothing, laundering, furnishing and maintenance of the house she plays the leading role. As an administrator, she organises various social functions in the family for social development. She also acts as a director of the recreation. She plans more recreational activities to meet the needs of young and old members of the family.

A Manager of Family Income

Woman acts the humble manager of the family income. It is her responsibility to secure a maximum return from every rupee spent. She always prefers to prepare a large budget instead of a deficit budget. She is very calculating loss and gains while spending money. She distributes the income judiciously. The woman in the family also contributes to the income of the family through her own earning within or outside the home. She has a positive contribution to the family income by the work. She performs in the house and uses waste products for productive purposes.

As a Mother

The whole burden of childbearing and the more significant part of the childbearing task are carried out by the woman in the family. She is responsible for the child's habit of self-control, orderliness, industriousness, theft or honesty. She is responsible for the maintenance of the discipline in the family. For her child, she is the first teacher. She transmits social heritage to the child. As there is intimate and sustained contact with the child, she can discover and nurture a child's unique traits aptitudes and attitudes which subsequently play the leading role in the shaping of his personality. She is the family health officer. She is concerned about the physical wellbeing of every member of the family, the helpless infant, the sickly child, the adolescent youth, and senescent parent. She organises the home and its activities in such a way so that each member of the family has proper food, enough amount of sleep and sufficient recreation.

The woman performs the role of wife, partner, organiser, administrator, director, re-creator, disburser, economist, mother, disciplinarian, teacher, health officer, artist and queen in the family at the same time. Apart from it, a woman plays a vital role in the socio-economic development of the society. Modern education and modern economic life use to compel woman more and more to leave the narrow sphere of the family circle and work side by side for the enrichment of society.

Summary, Main Findings and Suggestion for Future Study

This section includes a brief re-statement of the problem, a description of the procedure used the discussion of findings and conclusion of the study. After analysing the data, the investigator will prepare the report by the results of the investigation and make suggestions for future research.

Conclusion

Thus women play various roles as a wife, administrator and leader of household, manager, a mother and so on in the society. They must be treated equally and given respect. Education of the women eventually helps in the development of the society.

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